

Management of a Circumferential Infrabony Defect Using Freeze Dried Bone Allograft and Platelet Rich Fibrin: A Case Report

Soumya Parmar¹
 Mohd Rehan²
 Aditi Dhama³
 Manish Khatri⁴
 Mansi Bansal⁵
 Mayank Gupta⁶

PG Student¹
 Department of Periodontology
 Institute of Dental Studies & Technologies (IDST)
 Modinagar

Professor²
 Department of Periodontology
 Institute of Dental Studies & Technologies (IDST)
 Modinagar

PG Student³
 Department of Periodontology
 Institute of Dental Studies & Technologies (IDST)
 Modinagar

Professor⁴
 Department of Periodontology
 Institute of Dental Studies & Technologies (IDST)
 Modinagar

Professor & Head⁵
 Department of Periodontology
 Institute of Dental Studies & Technologies (IDST)
 Modinagar

Senior Lecturer⁶
 Department of Periodontology
 Institute of Dental Studies & Technologies (IDST)
 Modinagar

Submitted 23 February 2026
 Accepted 26 February 2026
 Published 11 April 2026

Access this Article Online Website: www.healtalk.in DOI	Quick Response Code
--	---------------------

Abstract

Background: Periodontitis is a chronic inflammatory disease characterized by progressive destruction of the periodontal supporting tissues, often leading to the formation of deep infrabony defects. These defects pose significant functional and esthetic challenges and are commonly resistant to non-surgical periodontal therapy alone. While conventional surgical approaches such as open flap debridement improve access and pocket reduction, true periodontal regeneration remains limited. Hence, regenerative modalities using bone grafts and biologic agents like platelet rich fibrin have gained prominence to promote restoration of the lost periodontal apparatus.

Aim: The aim of this study was to evaluate the role of a Freeze Dried bone graft substitute in the management of a circumferential infrabony defect in a mandibular left second molar in a patient diagnosed with localised periodontitis.

Methodology: A circumferential defect of 6 mm around the mandibular molar was evident after debridement. The defect was filled up with a FDBA bone graft substitute and covered with a PRF membrane.

Results: The site showed significant bony fill at the end of 9 months with reduction in probing depth to normal. The results were well maintained at the time of last follow-up at 12 months post-operatively.

Conclusion: The use of freeze dried bone allograft in combination with platelet rich fibrin demonstrated predictable and stable periodontal regeneration in the management of a circumferential infrabony defect, with sustained clinical and radiographic improvements observed up to 12 months post-operatively.

Keywords: Circumferential infrabony defect, Localized Periodontitis, FDBA bone allograft

Introduction

Periodontitis is a complex inflammatory condition that results in the progressive destruction of the supporting periodontal structures, ultimately leading to alveolar bone loss.¹ One of the common sequelae of periodontal breakdown is the formation of deep infrabony defects (IBDs), which are strongly associated with disease progression and eventual tooth loss.² These defects compromise masticatory efficiency and also adversely affect speech, facial aesthetics, and overall quality of life.³ Goldman and Cohen classified intrabony defects based on the number of remaining osseous walls into one wall, two wall, and three wall defects.⁴

Following effective supragingival plaque control, which constitutes the first phase of periodontal therapy, scaling and root planing (SRP) is performed as the second phase of active treatment. SRP aims to remove subgingival plaque and calculus, thereby eliminating

primary etiological factors.⁵ Nevertheless, residual deep pockets often persist, particularly in areas exhibiting infrabony bone loss, thereby necessitating surgical intervention.^{5,6}

Open flap debridement (OFD) is a widely used surgical approach that enhances access to deep periodontal defects and facilitates reduction in probing pocket depth. However, histologic evidence suggests that healing following OFD predominantly occurs through the formation of a long junctional epithelium rather than true periodontal regeneration.⁷

In contrast, regenerative periodontal therapy seeks to restore the lost attachment apparatus, including alveolar bone, periodontal ligament, and cementum.^{8,9} Healing characterized by epithelial attachment,

How to Cite This Article : Parmar et al. -

fibrous adhesion, ankylosis, or root resorption is considered periodontal repair rather than regeneration. Various regenerative techniques, such as modified Widman flap procedures with or without bone grafts and guided tissue regeneration (GTR), have been employed to achieve this objective. Although autogenous bone is considered the gold standard graft material, its clinical use is limited by donor site morbidity and insufficient availability. To address these limitations, bone allografts such as freeze dried bone allograft (FDBA) have been introduced as alternatives.^{11,12}

FDBA provides an osteoconductive framework and has shown favorable outcomes in periodontal regenerative procedures. More recently, platelet rich fibrin (PRF), introduced by Choukroun and colleagues, has gained attention as a second generation platelet concentrate due to its ease of preparation and fully autologous nature.^{13,14} The present study was aimed to evaluate the role of a Freeze Dried bone graft substitute in the management of a circumferential infrabony defect in a mandibular left second molar in a patient diagnosed with localised periodontitis.

Case Report

A 45 year old male patient reported with the chief complaint of bleeding and swelling of gums in relation to left lower tooth since 10 days. On examination there was a periodontal pocket of 6 mm in mandibular left second molar (Figure 1). The probing depth was 5 mm on mesial aspect and 6mm on distal aspect of second molar (Figure 2), and 5 mm on third molar. There was no tenderness or pus discharge. Radiograph revealed infrabony defects on distal aspect of 37 (Figure 3). The treatment plan was to carry out a complete debridement in 36-38 region and place a PRF membrane alone with the FDBA bone graft substitute to fill the defect.

Surgical Technique

A mucoperiosteal flap was raised from 36 to 38 region by using Kirkland crevicular flap to ensure maximum coverage of the grafted site. The flap was extended to include one tooth on either side of the defect site so as to allow adequate reflection without giving a vertical incision. After complete removal of the granulation tissue and complete debridement, a circumferential defect of 6 mm was present around 37 (Figure 4). The freeze dried bone graft substitute was placed in the defect to fill it completely (Figure 5) and then covered with a resorbable PRF membrane (Figure 6). The flap was sutured approximating it on both buccal and lingual aspects to completely cover the membrane (Figure 7).

Figure 1: Pre-operative

Figure 2: Probing Depth 6mm

Figure 3: OPG

Figure 4: Circumferential Defect

Figure 5: FDBA Placement

Figure 6: Placement of PRF Membrane

Figure 7: Suture Placement

Post-surgical treatment and follow-up

The patient was given plaque control instructions that included use of 0.12% Chlorhexidine rinse twice daily and to avoid tooth brushing in the operated quadrant. The sutures were removed 10 days following surgery. The Chlorhexidine rinse was advised for 2 weeks. The patient was advised to brush in the operated segment using a soft toothbrush. The patient was put on regular recall at 1, 3, 6, 9 & 12 months. The symptoms of bleeding and swelling had disappeared with a reduction in probing depth of 3mm at 3 months and after 6 months recall. Patient was comfortable with no recurrence of symptoms (Figure 8). At the 9 month recall, radiograph showed significant bony fill, evident as increase in

radioopacity and these results were maintained at the time of the last recall at 12 months (Figure 9).

Figure 8: Probing Depth Reduction

Figure 9: 12 Month Recall

Discussion

Regeneration of periodontal infrabony defects remains a biologic and clinical challenge due to the complex architecture of the periodontal attachment apparatus. As stated by Melcher¹⁵, true periodontal regeneration requires the coordinated formation of new alveolar bone, periodontal ligament, and cementum, which is difficult to achieve consistently with conventional therapy. Cortellini and Tonetti¹⁶ emphasized that defect morphology, particularly deep and contained defects, plays a crucial role in determining regenerative outcomes. In the present case, the circumferential infrabony defect around mandibular second molar provided a favorable environment for regenerative intervention.

Bone grafting has long been considered a cornerstone of periodontal regenerative therapy. Histologic studies by Mellonig and Bowers¹⁷ demonstrated that bone grafts can promote new bone and attachment formation under optimal conditions. Reynolds et al¹⁸ reported that alloplastic and some allogenic grafts primarily act as space fillers rather than true osteoinductive materials. Freeze dried bone allograft (FDBA), although predominantly osteoconductive, has shown predictable clinical improvements in probing depth reduction and radiographic bone fill, as described by Mellonig.

The addition of platelet rich fibrin (PRF) introduces a biologically active component to the regenerative approach. Choukroun et al¹³ first described PRF as a second generation platelet concentrate capable of releasing growth factors such as PDGF, TGF- β , and VEGF over a sustained period. Dohan Ehrenfest et al¹⁴ highlighted that PRF acts as a fibrin scaffold facilitating cell migration, angiogenesis, and wound stabilization. Furthermore, in vitro studies by He et al. demonstrated enhanced proliferation of osteoblasts and periodontal ligament fibroblasts in the presence of PRF.

Clinical studies have supported the adjunctive use of PRF with bone grafts. A randomized clinical trial by Thorat et al¹⁹ showed significantly greater probing depth reduction and radiographic

defect fill when PRF was combined with FDBA compared to FDBA alone. Similarly, Pradeep et al²⁰ reported superior clinical attachment gain in infrabony defects treated with PRF and bone graft combinations. The synergistic effect observed may be attributed to PRF's ability to accelerate soft tissue healing while stabilizing the graft material. The favorable clinical and radiographic outcomes observed in this case over a 12-month follow-up are consistent with findings reported by Cortellini et al¹⁶, who emphasized the importance of patient plaque control and regular maintenance in sustaining regenerative results. Thus, the combined use of PRF and FDBA appears to be a predictable and biologically sound approach for managing periodontal infrabony defects.

Conclusion

This case report highlights the successful management of a circumferential infrabony defect associated with localized periodontitis using freeze dried bone allograft in combination with platelet rich fibrin. The regenerative approach resulted in significant probing depth reduction and satisfactory radiographic evidence of bone fill. The use of PRF likely enhanced wound healing and graft stabilization due to its biologically active growth factors. Clinical outcomes were favorable and well maintained throughout the follow-up period. The patient exhibited good periodontal stability with no signs of disease progression. This case supports the effectiveness of combining bone graft substitutes with autologous biologic modifiers in periodontal regeneration. However, long-term studies with larger sample sizes are required to validate these findings and establish definitive clinical protocols.

References

1. Papapanou PN, Wennstrom JL. The angular bony defect as indicator of further alveolar bone loss. *J Clin Periodontol* 1991;18: 317–322.
2. Papapanou PN, Tonetti MS. Diagnosis and epidemiology of periodontal osseous lesions. *Periodontol 2000* 2000; 22: 8–21.
3. Rams TE, Listgarten MA, Slots J. Radiographic alveolar bone morphology and progressive periodontitis. *J Periodontol* 2018; 89: 424–430.
4. Goldman HM, Cohen DW. The Infrabony Pocket: Classification and Treatment. *J Periodontol* 1958; 29: 272–291.
5. Sanz M, Herrera D, Kebschull M, Chapple I, Jepsen S, Berglundh T et al. EFP Workshop Participants and Methodological Consultants et al. Treatment of stage I-III periodontitis-The EFP S3 level clinical practice guideline. *J Clin Periodontol* 2020; 47: 4–60.
6. Suvan J, Leira Y, Sancho FM, Graziani F, Derks J, Tomasi C. Subgingival instrumentation for treatment of periodontitis. A systematic review. *J Clin Periodontol* 2020; 47: 155–175.
7. Heitz-Mayfield LJ, Lang NP. Surgical and nonsurgical periodontal therapy. Learned and unlearned concepts. *Periodontol 2000* 2013; 62: 218–231.
8. Caton J, Nyman S. Histometric evaluation of periodontal surgery I. The modified Widman flap procedure. *J Clin Periodontol* 1980; 7: 212–223.
9. Caton J, Nyman S, Zander H. Histometric evaluation of periodontal surgery. II. Connective tissue attachment levels after four regenerative procedures. *J Clin Periodontol* 1980; 7: 224–231.
10. Laurell L, Gottlow J, Zybutz M, Persson R. Treatment of intrabony defects by different surgical procedures. A literature review. *J Periodontol* 1998; 69: 303–313.

11. Polson AM. Berlin Germany: Quintessence Publishing. Periodontal Regeneration - Current Status and Directions; 1994: 11–20.
12. Committee on Research, Science and Therapy of the American Academy of Periodontology. Tissue banking of bone allografts used in periodontal regeneration. *J Periodontol* 2001; 72: 834–838.
13. Choukroun J, Adda F, Schoeffler C, Vervelle A. Une opportunité en para-implantologie: le PRF Implantodontie 2000; 42: 55–62.
14. Dohan DM, Choukroun J, Diss A, Dohan SL, Dohan AJ, Mouhyi J et al. Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF): a second-generation platelet concentrate. Part I: technological concepts and evolution. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod* 2006; 101: 37–44.
15. Melcher AH. On the repair potential of periodontal tissues. *J Periodontol* 1976; 47: 256–260.
16. Cortellini P, Tonetti MS. Clinical concepts for regenerative therapy in intrabony defects. *Periodontol 2000* 2015; 68: 282–307.
17. Mellonig JT. Freeze-dried bone allografts in periodontal reconstructive surgery. *Dent Clin North Am* 1991; 35: 505–520.
18. Reynolds MA, Aichelmann Reidy ME, Branch Mays GL. Regeneration of periodontal tissue: bone replacement grafts. *Dent Clin North Am* 2010; 54: 55–71.
19. Thorat M, Pradeep AR, Pallavi B. Clinical effect of PRF in infrabony defects. *J Clin Periodontol* 2011; 38: 925–932.
20. Pradeep AR, Rao NS, Agarwal E, Bajaj P, Kumari M. PRF combined with bone graft in periodontal defects. *J Periodontol* 2012; 83: 1499–1507.